

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0001

\ELANf 0.000

\ELANf 9.754

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 0.000 9.754

\t	<i>Eh, bijo?</i>	<i>p^hradokrudok</i>	<i>leda,</i>	<i>dzapk^ho</i>	<i>pronpron_</i>	<i>lek^hen</i>	<i>dert^haŋ</i>	<i>be?</i>	<i>in,</i>						
\m	<i>eh bi</i>	<i>-o?</i>	<i>p^hradok</i>	<i>le</i>	<i>-da</i>	<i>dzap</i>	<i>-k^ho</i>	<i>pron</i>	<i>-k^hen</i>	<i>dert^ha</i>	<i>be?</i>	<i>in</i>			
\g	ehm	ana	-erg	slander(<TB)	do	-ipfv	behind(<TB)	-loc	curse(<BP)	-agn	much(<TM)	cop.ex	say		
\p	<i>interj.pron.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>n.</i>		<i>v.t.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>postp.</i>		<i>-suff.</i>	<i>v.t.</i>		<i>-nom.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>cop.</i>	<i>v.t.&v.i.</i>

\t *ajisabakpi.*

\m *ajisa* *-bak* *-ni*

\g female.family.members-pl -dat

\p *n.* *-suff.* *-suff.*

\f Ehm, (Jomo) says they, committing slander, there are many of those that curse all the female family members behind the back. [CHUK221212D2A_0001]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0002

\ELANf 9.754

\ELANf 14.643

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 9.754 14.643

\t	<i>tɛ^hoj</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>dejt^hakpa</i>	<i>dursa</i>	<i>k^haŋsana</i>		<i>katiraŋ</i>	<i>ɕetbaŋlo?</i>		
\m	<i>tɛ^hoj</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>dej -t^hakpa</i>	<i>dursa</i>	<i>k^haŋsa</i>	<i>=na</i>	<i>kati</i>	<i>=raŋ</i>	<i>ɕet -baŋ</i>	<i>=olo?</i>
\g	this.side	mother	be.big -sds	grave(<TB)	graveyard(<TSH)	=conf	small	=emph	exit -neg.prs	=then
\p	<i>adv.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>v.i. -suff.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>adj.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>v.i. -suff.</i>	<i>=conj.</i>

\f This side not even a small graveyard appears (lit. even a small graveyard does not appear) (from) the seniormost mother. [CHUK221212D2A_0002]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0003

\ELANf 14.643

\ELANf 20.987

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 14.643 20.987

\t *dʒaploʔ* *pronpron dertɕ^ha* *baŋba* *leloŋ,* *nar* *ajisabakni.*

\m *dʒap* *-loʔ* *pronpron dertɕ^ha* *baŋ* *-ba* *le* *-loŋ* *nar* *ajisa* *-bak* *-ni*

\g behind(<TB) -abl curse much(<TM) not.be1 -nom do -prf 2pl female.family.members-pl -dat

\p *postp.* *-suff.* *expr.* *adv.* *cop.v.* *-suff.* *v.t.* *-suff.* *pron.* *n.* *-suff.* *-suff.*

\f From behind (they) have cursed you female family members very much. [CHUK221212D2A_0003]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0004
\ELAN# 14.643
\ELAN# 20.987
\ELAN# Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 14.643 20.987
\t zepa pronɲma inma hoʔt^heʔ, jɪŋ batsumsena!
\m zepa pron -ma in -ma hoʔ =t^heʔ jɪŋ ba- tsum -se =na
\g many(TSD) curse(<BP) -imp say -imp now =add heart(TB) neg- be.satisfied(<TB) -cond =conf
\p adj. v.t. -suff. v.t.&v.i. -suff. adv. =clit. n. pref.- v.i. -suff. =clit.
\f Tell them to curse more again, if not satisfied! [CHUK221212D2A_0004]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0005
\ELANf 20.987
\ELANf 25.710
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 20.987 25.710
\t *Lese, ken odok ban.*
\m *le -se ken odok ban*
\g do -cond obstacle(R)(<TB) big not.bel
\p *v.t. -suff. n. adj. cop.v.*

\f Nonetheless, there is no big obstacle / the obstacle is not big. [CHUK221212D2A_0005]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0006

\ELANf 25.710

\ELANf 29.529

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 25.710 29.529

\t t^he, t^hoj-ta nan-k^horaŋ be?

\m t^he t^hoj -ta nan -k^ho =raŋ be?

\g here this.side -all in -loc =emph cop.ex

\p adv. adv. -suff. postp. -suff. =clit. cop.

\f There, (it - the 'path') is towards this side, to the inside only. [CHUK221212D2A_0006]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0007

\ELANf 29.529

\ELANf 33.514

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 29.529 33.514

\t *t^hej-ta* *ose* *huma katiraŋ* *ɕetbaŋ.*

\m *t^he* *-ta ose* *huma kati =raŋ* *ɕet -baŋ*

\g the.other.side -all like.that path small =emph exit -neg.prs

\p *adv.* *-suff. dem.* *n.* *adj.* *=clit.* *v.i.* *-suff.*

\f Towards the other side, not even a small path like that appears (lit. only a small path like that does not appear).
[CHUK221212D2A_0007]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0008
\ELANf 33.514
\ELANf 37.175
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 33.514 37.175
\t *Ate^ha* *he,* *p^hilu* *la.*
\m *ate^ha* *he* *p^hilu* *la*
\g good(HIN) cop(HIN) good(TSD) cop(TSH)
\p *adj.* *cop.* *adj.* *cop.*

\f It is good, it is good. [CHUK221212D2A_0008]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0009

\ELANf 33.514

\ELANf 37.175

\ELANf Ai Jomba

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 33.514 37.175

\t *Woj p^hak puŋma inse eutbaŋ.*

\m *woj p^hak puŋ -ma in -se eut -baŋ*

\g 3sg liquor drink -imp say -cond heed -neg.prs

\p *pron. n. v.t. -suff. v.t.&v.i. -suff. v.t. -suff.*

\f When telling him to drink liquor (he) doesn't agree. [CHUK221212D2A_0009]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0010
\ELANf 37.175
\ELANf 38.609
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 37.175 38.609
\t *perimts^{he}...*
\m *rimts^{he}*
\g contagious.disease(<TB)
\p *n.*

\f The great epidemic... [CHUK221212D2A_0010]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0011
\ELANf 37.175
\ELANf 38.609
\ELANf Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 37.175 38.609
\t *tʰabaji nar?*
\m *tʰa -ba =ji nar*
\g eat -nom =q1 2pl
\p *v.t.&v.i. -suff. =part. pron.*

\f Did you eat? [CHUK221212D2A_0011]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0012
\ELANf 38.609
\ELANf 40.501
\ELANf Dorji Chojjom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 38.609 40.501
\t *Baŋ, mo tɕ^hawaŋu.*
\m *baŋ mo tɕ^ha -wa -ŋu*
\g not.be1 come.on(<TSH) eat -go -adh
\p *v.i. interj. v.i.&v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f No (we didn't), come let's go and eat. [CHUK221212D2A_0012]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0013
\ELANf 40.501
\ELANf 46.943
\ELANf Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 40.501 46.943
\t *tɛ^hamaba* *garna.*
\m *tɛ^ha* *-ma* *-ba* *gar* *=na*
\g eat *-finish* *-nom* *1pl* *=conf*
\p *v.t.&v.i.* *-s.v.* *-suff.* *pron.* *=clit.*

\f But we finished eating. [CHUK221212D2A_0013]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0014

\ELANf 40.501

\ELANf 46.943

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 40.501 46.943

\t	<i>perimts^he</i>	<i>p^hetbaʔ</i>	<i>beʔ.</i>	<i>ziwa,</i>	<i>zakpa,</i>	<i>gandolan</i>	
\m	<i>rimts^he</i>	<i>p^het</i>	<i>-baʔ</i>	<i>beʔ</i>	<i>ziwa</i>	<i>zakpa</i>	<i>gamaŋ =raŋ</i>
\g	contagious.disease(<TB)	arrive	-inf	cop.ex	peace.ritual(R)	(<TB)fencing.ritual	additionally =emph
\p	<i>n.</i>	<i>v.i.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>cop.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>adv. =clit.</i>

\t *lema lumpak^ho.*

\m *le -ma luŋpa -k^ho*

\g do -imp valley(<TB)-loc

\p *v.t. -suff. n. -suff.*

\f It is so that the contagious disease will arrive. Additionally conduct peace and fencing rituals in the valley.
[CHUK221212D2A_0014]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0015

\ELANf 46.943

\ELANf 58.497

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 46.943 58.497

\t	<i>Lak^huŋ soko, ote^hi lak^hun namla laŋpej,</i>	<i>duhutma hin ɕorŋon oŋt^hej</i>	<i>in.</i>
\m	<i>lak^huŋ ho? ote^hi lak^hun namla laŋpej</i>	<i>duhutma hin ɕorŋon oŋ -t^heʔ=aj</i>	<i>in</i>
\g	later now this behind month around(<TSD)	woman one loss go -sbjv.npst=ok	say
\p	adv. adv. dem. adj. n. postp.	n. num. n. v.i. -suff.=part.	v.t.&v.i.

\f (It - the Jomo) says later (from) now, sometime this coming month, a woman would die ok (lit. would go as a loss). [CHUK221212D2A_0015]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0016

\ELANf 58.497

\ELANf 65.327

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 58.497 65.327

\t *bje t^hup, ot^hi naŋk^ho baŋ. bje t^hup zup naŋk^ho beʔ, dʒagarbastik^hoŋi*
\m *be t^hup ot^hi naŋ -k^ho baŋ be t^hup zup naŋ -k^ho beʔ dʒagarbasti -k^ho =ŋi*
\g down village this in -loc not.be1 down village end in -loc cop.ex Jagarbasti -loc =q1
\p *n. n. dem. postp. -suff. cop.v. n. n. n. postp. -suff. cop. prop.n. -suff. =part.*

\t *haʔkopi?*

\m *haʔ =ŋi*

\g where =q1

\p *interrog. =part.*

\f The village down, it is not around here. It is around the lower end of the village, whether in Jagarbasti or where?
[CHUK221212D2A_0016]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0017

\ELANf 65.327

\ELANf 69.814

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 65.327 69.814

\t *Adi lese bacutba? It^he? inde? t^hej humaraŋ cətɟude?*
\m *adi le -se ba- ɟut -ba? i -t^he? in -de? t^he huma =raŋ ɟet -ɟu -de?*
\g *how do -cond neg- heed -inf die -subj:npst say -prs here path =emph exit -stay -prs*
\p *interrog. v.t. -suff. pref.- v.t. -suff. v.i. -suff. v.t.&v.i. -suff. adv. n. =clit. v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f No matter what is done (lit. however is done), it won't help (lit. it won't heed). (She - the woman) would die (it - the Jomo) says. Here, the road itself is coming out. [CHUK221212D2A_0017]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0018

\ELANf 69.814

\ELANf 72.582

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 69.814 72.582

\t *Onowuma* *dzent^hakpao?* *amak^ho* *tsaktsik* *ban.*

\m *onowuma* *dzen -t^hakpa -o?* *ama -k^ho* *tsaktsik* *ban*

\g younger.female.siblings small -sds -erg mother -loc sundries(<TB) not.be1

\p *n.* *adj. -suff.* *-suff. n.* *-suff. expr.* *cop.v.*

\f The youngest daughter does not obey the mother a bit (lit. does not have a little for the mother).
[CHUK221212D2A_0018]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0019

\ELANf 72.582

\ELANf 74.524

\ELANf TowTshering

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 72.582 74.524

\t *Wamma? adi be?ni dojma apa. Wamma? adi lont^he?ni.*

\m *wam -a? adi be? =ni doj -ma apa wam -a? adi lon -t^he? =ni*

\g *house -gen how cop.ex =q1 look -imp father house -gen how come -sbjv.npst =q1*

\p *n. -suff. interrog. cop. =part. v.t. -suff. n. n. -suff. interrog. v.i.&v.t. -suff. =part.*

\f Look at how it is at home (lit. of the house) father. How would it be at home? [CHUK221212D2A_0019]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0020

\ELANf 74.524

\ELANf 76.582

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 74.524 76.582

\t *Ama naŋ-k^ho gomd̥zude?*

\m *ama naŋ -k^ho gom -d̥zu -de?*

\g mother in -loc be.motionless -stay -prs

\p *n. postp. -suff. v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f The mother is staying motionless inside (i.e. the mother is in full control, there is no problem in the house).
[CHUK221212D2A_0020]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0021
\ELANf 76.582
\ELANf 78.845
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 76.582 78.845
\t *ʃa* *Now!*
\m *ja* *Now*
\g here.you.are Ngow
\p *interj.* *prop. n.*

\f Here you are Ngow! [CHUK221212D2A_0021]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0022
\ELANf 76.582
\ELANf 78.845
\ELANf Dorji Chojjom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 76.582 78.845
\t *ʃa.*
\m *ja*
\g go.ahead
\p *interj.*

\f Ok. [CHUK221212D2A_0022]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0023
\ELANf 78.845
\ELANf 80.743
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 78.845 80.743
\t *Ot^{hi} eiŋ badi-ŋi?*
\m *ot^{hi} eiŋ ba- di =ŋi*
\g this wood neg- burn =q1
\p *dem. n. pref.- v.t. =part.*

\f Won't you burn this wood? [CHUK221212D2A_0023]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0024
\ELANf 78.845
\ELANf 80.743
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 78.845 80.743
\t *p^hradok...*
\m *p^hradok*
\g slander(<TB)
\p *n.*

\f Slander... [CHUK221212D2A_0024]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0025

\ELANf 80.743

\ELANf 84.857

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 80.743 84.857

\t *p^hradokrudok lek^hen prɔŋk^henno?* *nasadansa baŋ in aj.*

\m *p^hradok le -k^hen prɔŋ -k^hen -o?* *nasadansa baŋ in aj*

\g slander(<TB) do -agn curse(<BP) -agn -erg many.thingsnot.be1 say ok

\p *n. v.t. -nom. v.t. -nom. -suff. n. cop.v. v.t.&v.i. interj.*

\f Those that slander and those that curse say whatever not ok (lit. not many different things).
[CHUK221212D2A_0025]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0026

\ELANf 84.857

\ELANf 90.310

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 84.857 90.310

\t *Dokpa* *han toshatt^he?* *in. Ose hin lese, kikba? be?*

\m *dokpa hin tos -hat -t^he?* *in ose hin le -se kik -ba? be?*

\g dispel.ritual(R)(<TB)one throw -lose -sbjv.npst say like.that one do -cond be.ok -inf cop.ex

\p *n. num. v.t. -s.v. -suff. v.t.&v.i. dem. num. v.t. -suff. v.i. -suff. cop.*

\f (She - Jomo) says a possession ritual would be conducted (lit. thrown away). If doing one like that, it is so that it will be ok. [CHUK221212D2A_0026]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0027
\ELANf 84.857
\ELANf 90.310
\ELANf Dorji Chojjom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 84.857 90.310
\t *Milo??*
\m *mi -lo?*
\g *who -abl*
\p *interrog. -suff.*

\f From whom? [CHUK221212D2A_0027]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0028

\ELANf 90.310

\ELANf 95.049

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 90.310 95.049

\t	<i>tɛ^hej</i>	<i>awu</i>	<i>dejt^hakpat^he?</i>	<i>tanbu</i>	<i>be?</i>	<i>Amat^he?</i>	<i>tanbu</i>	<i>be?</i>			
\m	<i>tɛ^he</i>	<i>awu</i>	<i>dej -t^hakpa</i>	<i>=t^he?</i>	<i>tanbu</i>	<i>be?</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>=t^he?</i>	<i>tanbu</i>	<i>be?</i>	
\g	here	elder.sister	be.big	-sds	=add	reliable(<TSH)	cop.ex	mother	=add	reliable(<TSH)	cop.ex
\p	<i>adv.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>v.i.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>adj.</i>	<i>cop.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>adj.</i>	<i>cop.</i>

\f This eldest sister here is reliable too. The mother is also reliable. [CHUK221212D2A_0028]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0029
\ELANf 90.310
\ELANf 95.049
\ELANf Dorji Choijom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 90.310 95.049
\t *cutbarbejlo?* *aji* *danna?* Tow *ts^herij.*
\m *cut -bar =be?=aj =olo? aji dan -a? tow ts^herij*
\g heed -neg.prs =cop.ex=ok =then grandmother and -gen Tow Tshering
\p *v.t. -suff. =cop.=part. =conj. n. conj. -suff. prop.n. prop.n.*
\f Mother-in-law and Tow Tshering don't heed ok! [CHUK221212D2A_0029]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0030
\ELANf 95.049
\ELANf 99.829
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 95.049 99.829
\t *corŋon, corŋon tsaji ban.*
\m *corŋon corŋon tsaji ban*
\g loss loss never(<TB) not.be1
\p *n. n. adv. cop.v.*

\f There is never any loss. [CHUK221212D2A_0030]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0031
\ELANf 95.049
\ELANf 99.829
\ELANf Dorji Choijom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 95.049 99.829
\t *ɕorɲon abe p^hetlont^heʔ?*
\m *ɕorɲon abe p^het -lon -t^heʔ*
\g loss what arrive -come -sbjv.npst
\p *n. interrog. v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f What (kind of) loss might arrive (here)? [CHUK221212D2A_0031]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0032

\ELANf 99.829

\ELANf 101.710

\ELANf Dorji Chojjom

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 99.829 101.710

\t *Raŋbeʔt^hoŋt^heʔ* *ɕetse* *abe* *lebaʔ* *ja* *oloʔʔ*

\m *raŋ* *-bi-jaʔ* *-t^hoŋ* =*t^heʔ* *ɕet* *-se* *abe* *le* *-baʔ* *ja* *oloʔ*

\g ego(<TB) -refl-gen -assoc =add exit -cond what do -inf q2 then

\p *pron.* *-suff.-suff.* *-suff.* =*clit.* *v.i.* *-suff.* *interrog.* *v.t.* *-suff.* *part.* *conj.*

\f Even if (it - the loss) appears upon oneself then what will (one) do? [CHUK221212D2A_0032]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0033
 \ELANf 101.710
 \ELANf 108.690
 \ELANf Atha Kesang
 \sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 101.710 108.690
 \t *bje dzagarbastik^ho kikt^heʔni, pejbe t^hup zupk^ho kikt^heʔni?*
 \m *be dzagarbasti -k^ho kik -t^heʔ =ʃi pejbe t^hup zup -k^ho kik -t^heʔ =ʃi*
 \g down Jagarbasti -loc be.ok -sbjv.npst =q1 that.down.there village end -loc be.ok -sbjv.npst =q1
 \p *n. prop.n. -suff. v.i. -suff. =part. adv. n. n. -suff. v.i. -suff. =part.*
 \f Whether it would be (lit. would be ok) down in Jagarabasti, or whether it would be down there at the end of the village? [CHUK221212D2A_0033]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0034

\ELANf 108.690

\ELANf 115.449

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 108.690 115.449

\t *Duhutma hin, ok^ho huma kati hin cətɟude? tɕ^hoj, tɕ^hojtɕ^hok.*

\m *duhutma hin ok^ho huma kati hin cət -ɟu -de? tɕ^hoj tɕ^hoj -cok*

\g woman one there path small one exit -stay -prs this.side this.side -side

\p *n. num. dem. n. adj. num. v.i. -s.v. -suff. adv. adv. -suff.*

\f A woman, there a small path is coming out this side, on this side. [CHUK221212D2A_0034]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0035

\ELANf 115.449

\ELANf 121.311

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 115.449 121.311

\t *Dursa* *k^haŋsa* *kati hin* *çetda,* *naŋk^ho* *wagirpaŋ.*

\m *dursa* *k^haŋsa* *kati hin* *çet -da* *naŋ -k^ho* *wa -gir -paŋ*

\g grave(<TB) graveyard(<TSH) small one exit -ipfv in -loc move -return -neg.prs

\p *n.* *n.* *adj.* *num.* *v.i.* *-suff.* *postp.* *-suff.* *v.i.* *-s.v.* *-suff.*

\f A small graveyard appearing, (it) does not return back inside. [CHUK221212D2A_0035]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0036

\ELANf 121.311

\ELANf 125.900

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 121.311 125.900

\t	<i>tʰej</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>hoʔ</i>	<i>naŋda</i>	<i>baŋ.</i>	<i>Amatʰeʔ</i>	<i>zoti</i>	<i>beʔ.</i>	<i>Wojtʰeʔ</i>	<i>zoti</i>		
\m	<i>tʰe</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>hoʔ</i>	<i>naŋda</i>	<i>baŋ</i>	<i>ama</i>	<i>=tʰeʔ</i>	<i>sotʰi</i>	<i>beʔ</i>	<i>woj =tʰeʔ</i>	<i>sotʰi</i>	
\g	here	mother	now	problem(<TB)	not.be1	mother	=add	fine(<TSD)	cop.ex	3sg	=add	fine(<TSD)
\p	<i>adv.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>cop.v.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>cop.</i>	<i>pron.</i>	<i>=clit.</i>	<i>adv.</i>

\t *beʔ.*

\m *beʔ*

\g cop.ex

\p *cop.*

\f The mother here has no problem (lit. (to) this mother here there is no problem now). The mother is fine too. She is fine as well. [CHUK221212D2A_0036]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0037

\ELANf 125.900

\ELANf 130.543

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 125.900 130.543

\t *tɕ^hej huma otɕ^hiloʔ beʔ Talala ɕetdʒudeʔ, tɕ^hej.*

\m *tɕ^he huma otɕ^hi -loʔ beʔ talala ɕet -dʒu -deʔ tɕ^he*

\g here path this -abl cop.ex directly exit -stay -prs here

\p *adv. n. dem. -suff. cop. expr. v.i. -s.v. -suff. adv.*

\f Here, the path is from here. It is coming out directly, here. [CHUK221212D2A_0037]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0038

\ELANf 130.543

\ELANf 133.841

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 130.543 133.841

\t *Ot̪ʰit̪ʰe?* *zoti* *be?* *Ot̪ʰi huma boju woj.*

\m *ot̪ʰi =t̪ʰe?* *sot̪ʰi* *be?* *ot̪ʰi huma boju woj*

\g this =add fine(<TSD) cop.ex this path not.be2 3sg

\p *dem. =clit. adv.* *cop.* *dem. n.* *cop.v. pron.*

\f This here is fine too. This here, it is not a path.[CHUK221212D2A_0038]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0039
\ELANf 133.841
\ELANf 135.514
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 133.841 135.514
\t *Wojt^he?* *zoti* *be?*
\m *woj =t^he?* *sot^hi* *be?*
\g 3sg =add fine(<TSD) cop.ex
\p *pron. =clit. adv. cop.*

\f She is well too. [CHUK221212D2A_0039]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0040
\ELANf 135.514
\ELANf 139.182
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 135.514 139.182
\t *Ot^ho* *duhutma hin pankej* *lont^he?*
\m *ot^ho* *duhutma hin pankej* *lon* *-t^he?*
\g here.this.side woman one danger(<TB) come -sbjv.npst
\p *dem.* *n.* *num. n.* *v.i.&v.t. -suff.*

\f Here on this side a woman would be (in) danger. [CHUK221212D2A_0040]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0041

\ELANf 139.182

\ELANf 142.267

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 139.182 142.267

\t *dzen-cok hin be? Duhutma ose odok bojuba?*

\m *dzen -cok hin be? duhutma ose odok boju -ba?*

\g small -cde one cop.ex woman like.that big not.be2 -inf

\p *adj. -suff. num. cop. n. dem. adj. cop.v. -suff.*

\f (She) is a younger one (woman). The woman won't be that mature. [CHUK221212D2A_0041]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0042
\ELANf 142.267
\ELANf 144.718
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 142.267 144.718
\t *dzen-cok hin jankej lont^he?* *in.*
\m *dzen -cok hin jankej lon -t^he?* *in*
\g small -cde one danger(<TB) come -subj:npst say
\p *adj. -suff. num. n. v.i.&v.t. -suff. v.t.&v.i.*
\f (Jomo) says danger would come to a younger one (woman). [CHUK221212D2A_0042]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0043

\ELANf 144.718

\ELANf 151.369

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 144.718 151.369

\t *Adi gite^ha baden. Donno? k^hanj^hont^he?* *in.*
\m *adi gite^ha ba- den don -o? k^hanj -t^hon -t^he?* *in*
\g *how cop3 neg- know ghost(<TB) -erg lift.up -take -sbjv.npst say*
\p *interrog. cop. pref.- v.t. n. -suff. v.t. -s.v. -suff. v.t.&v.i.*

\f How it is (I) don't know. (Jomo) says a ghost would carry (her) away. [CHUK221212D2A_0043]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0044
\ELANf 151.369
\ELANf 156.698
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 151.369 156.698
\t *Rimte^he,* *rimte^he* *dzakadzoko p^hett^he?lo?*
\m *rimts^he* *rimts^he* *zakazoko p^het -t^he? =olo?*
\g contagious.disease(<TB)contagious.disease(<TB)messy arrive -sbjv.npst =then
\p *n.* *n.* *expr.* *v.i.* *-suff.* *=conj.*
\f The contagious disease, the messy contagious disease would arrive. [CHUK221212D2A_0044]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0045

\ELANf 156.698

\ELANf 162.393

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 156.698 162.393

\t *cit^he* *balon* *in,* *gala?* *wam nan-k^ho,* *garbe?*

\m *cit^he* *ba-* *lon* *in* *gala?* *wam nan* *-k^ho* *gar* *-bi-ja?*

\g death(TB) neg- come say 1pl.gen house in -loc 1pl -refl-gen

\p *n.* *pref.-* *v.i.&v.t.* *v.t.&v.i.* *pron.* *n.* *postp.* *-suff.* *pron.* *-suff.-suff.*

\f Death won't come (Jomo) says, inside our house, our own. [CHUK221212D2A_0045]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0046
\ELANf 162.393
\ELANf 163.349
\ELANf Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 162.393 163.349
\t *Adi inbej?*
\m *adi in =be?=aj*
\g *how say =cop.ex=ok*
\p *interrog. v.t.&v.i. =cop.=part.*

\f How does (Jomo) say huh? [CHUK221212D2A_0046]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0047
\ELANf 163.349
\ELANf 165.244
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 163.349 165.244
\t *t^hap tsarbu lema!*
\m *bejdup tsarbu le -ma*
\g hearth clean(TSB) do -imp
\p *n. adj. v.t. -suff.*
\f Make the hearth clean! [CHUK221212D2A_0047]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0048

\ELANf 165.244

\ELANf 170.875

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 165.244 170.875

\t	<i>Rimts^he</i>	<i>dzakadzoko</i>	<i>p^hett^he?lo?</i>	<i>Garbe?</i>	<i>wam</i>	<i>naŋk^hona</i>
\m	<i>rimts^he</i>	<i>zakazoko</i>	<i>p^het -t^he?</i>	<i>=olo?</i>	<i>gar =be?</i>	<i>wam naŋ -k^ho =na</i>
\g	contagious.disease(<TB)	messy	arrive -sbjv.npst	=then 1pl	=cop.ex	house in -loc =conf
\p	<i>n.</i>	<i>expr.</i>	<i>v.i. -suff.</i>	<i>=conj. pron. =clitic</i>	<i>n. postp. -suff. =clit.</i>	

\t	<i>naŋda</i>	<i>baŋba</i>	<i>in.</i>
\m	<i>naŋda</i>	<i>baŋ -ba</i>	<i>in</i>
\g	problem(<TB)	not.be1 -nom	say
\p	<i>n.</i>	<i>cop.v. -suff. v.t.&v.i.</i>	

\f The messy contagious disease would arrive. But there isn't a problem in our own house (Jomo) says.
[CHUK221212D2A_0048]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0049
\ELANf 170.875
\ELANf 171.880
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 170.875 171.880
\t *Ot^hi hukhatdej* *ɲow?*
\m *ot^hi huk -hat -dej* *ɲow*
\g this pour -lose -look Ngow
\p *dem. v.t. -s.v. -s.v. prop.n.*

\f Shall I pour this here out Ngow? [CHUK221212D2A_0049]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0050

\ELANf 171.880

\ELANf 178.391

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 171.880 178.391

\t *Otʰi tʰup zupkʰo kiktʰeʔni, dzagarbasti kiktʰeʔni, duhutma dzen-cok*
 \m *otʰi tʰup zup -kʰo kik -tʰeʔ =ni dzagarbasti kik -tʰeʔ =ni duhutma dzen -cok*
 \g this village end -loc be.ok -sbjv.npst =q1 Jagarbasti be.ok -sbjv.npst =q1 woman small -cds
 \p *dem. n. n. -suff. v.i. -suff. =part. prop.n. v.i. -suff. =part. n. adj. -suff.*

\t *hin lakʰun namlakʰo janpu janpu dzubaʔ in.*
 \m *hin lakʰun namla -kʰo janpu janpu dzu -baʔ in*
 \g one behind month -loc risky risky be -inf say
 \p *num. adj. n. -suff. adj. adj. cop.v. -suff. v.t.&v.i.*

\f Whether it would be at the end of this village here, or whether it would be in Jagarbasti, in the following month a younger woman will stay very much at risk (Jomo) says. [CHUK221212D2A_0050]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0051
\ELANf 178.391
\ELANf 180.621
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 178.391 180.621
\t *Naŋ zok lesena abe dʒut^he?*
\m *naŋ zok le -se =na abe dʒu -t^he?*
\g 2sg lie(<TSD) do -cond =conf what be -sbjv.npst
\p *pron. n. v.t. -suff. =clit. interrog. cop.v. -suff.*
\f If you tell a lie, what would it be? [CHUK221212D2A_0051]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0052
\ELANf 180.621
\ELANf 182.037
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 180.621 182.037
\t *Huma hin cetd̥zude?*
\m *huma hin cet -d̥zu -de?*
\g path one exit -stay -prs
\p *n. num. v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f A path is coming out. [CHUK221212D2A_0052]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0053
\ELAN# 182.037
\ELAN# 186.960
\ELAN# Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 182.037 186.960
\t Ha! Zok *cetbacet*, *gaʔt^hoŋraŋ* *dojdzumana* oŋ!
\m ha zok *cet - ba- cet ga-aʔ -t^hoŋ =raŋ doj -dzu -ma =na oŋ*
\g ha lie(<TSD) exit - neg- exit 1sg-gen -assoc =emph look -stay -imp =conf right
\p *interj. n. v.i. - pref.- v.i. pron.-suff. -suff. =clit. v.t. -s.v. -suff. =clit. interj.*

\f Ha! Whether (it) comes out as a lie or not, but keep looking (Jomo) with me only right!
[CHUK221212D2A_0053]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0054

\ELANf 186.960

\ELANf 189.136

\ELANf Dorji Choijom

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 186.960 189.136

\t *Ot^hi ziwa takcak^ho ose budun it^he?* *inse,*
 \m *ot^hi ziwa takca -k^ho ose budun i -t^he?* *in -se*
 \g this peace.ritual(R)(<TB)prediction -loc like.that person die -sbjv.npst say -cond
 \p *dem. n. n. -suff. dem. n. v.i. -suff. v.t.&v.i. -suff.*

\t *ide?ci nomaraŋ.*
 \m *i -de? =ci noma =raŋ*
 \g die -prs =cop.as really(<TB)=emph
 \p *v.i. -suff. =cop. adv. =clit.*

\f If in this prediction of the peace ritual here (Jomo) says a person would die like that, (he) really dies for sure.
 [CHUK221212D2A_0054]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0055
\ELANf 189.136
\ELANf 193.009
\ELANf Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 189.136 193.009
\t Oŋ ci ana, denba?ci.
\m oŋ ci ana den -ba? =ci
\g yes cop.as right be.right -inf =cop.as
\p interj. cop. interj. v.i. -suff. =cop.

\f Yes it is right, it will surely be true. [CHUK221212D2A_0055]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0056
\ELAN# 189.136
\ELAN# 193.009
\ELAN# Dorji Choijom
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 189.136 193.009
\t *Baŋtaŋ abe-raŋ* *ba* *den*, *ogi* *dende?* *samde?* *ga-na*.
\m *baŋtaŋ abe* =*raŋ* *ba-* *den* -*se* *ogi* *den* -*de?* *sam* -*de?* *ga* =*na*
\g another what =emph neg- be.right -cond that be.right -prs think -prs 1sg =conf
\p *pron.* *interrog.* =*clit.* *pref.-* *v.i.* -*suff.* *dem.* *v.i.* -*suff.* *v.i.* -*suff.* *pron.* =*clit.*
\f Even if nothing else is true, still I think that that is right. [CHUK221212D2A_0056]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0057

\ELANf 193.009

\ELANf 199.853

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 193.009 199.853

\t	<i>tʰej</i> ,	<i>tʰoj-ta</i> ,	<i>tʰoj-ta</i> ,	<i>tʰej-ta</i>		<i>dursa</i>	<i>kʰaŋsa</i>	<i>ɕetbaŋ</i> .			
\m	<i>tʰe</i>	<i>tʰoj</i>	<i>-ta</i>	<i>tʰoj</i>	<i>-ta</i>	<i>tʰe</i>	<i>-ta</i>	<i>dursa</i>	<i>kʰaŋsa</i>	<i>ɕet</i>	<i>-baŋ</i>
\g	here	this.side	-all	this.side	-all	the.other.side	-all	grave(<TB)	graveyard(<TSH)	exit	-neg.prs
\p	<i>adv.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>adv.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>n.</i>	<i>v.i.</i>	<i>-suff.</i>

\t	<i>Namda</i>	<i>be?</i>
\m	<i>namda</i>	<i>be?</i>
\g	good(<TM)	cop.ex
\p	<i>adj.</i>	<i>cop.</i>

\f This here, towards this side, towards that side, towards that side a graveyard does not come out. It is good.
[CHUK221212D2A_0057]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0058
\ELANf 199.853
\ELANf 200.478
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 199.853 200.478
\t *Mi?*
\m *mi*
\g *who*
\p *interrog.*

\f Who? [CHUK221212D2A_0058]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0059
\ELANf 200.478
\ELANf 201.795
\ELANf Ai Jomba
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 200.478 201.795
\t *tɕ^homp^hej ibak^hoci!*
\m *tɕ^homp^hej i -ba -k^ho =ci*
\g Chomphey die -nom -loc =cop.as
\p *prop.n. v.i. -suff. -suff. =cop.*
\f Exactly (like) when Chomphey died! [CHUK221212D2A_0059]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0060

\ELANf 201.795

\ELANf 203.715

\ELANf TowTshering

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 201.795 203.715

\t *Oŋ ci ose inji oŋ.*

\m *oŋ ci ose in -ji oŋ*

\g *yes cop.as like.that say -pret right*

\p *interj. cop. dem. v.t.&v.i. -suff. interj.*

\f Yes that's correct, (Jomo) said like that right! [CHUK221212D2A_0060]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0061
\ELANf 201.795
\ELANf 203.715
\ELANf Sang Tshomo
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 201.795 203.715
\t *Ama nar bistan t^hamabapi?*
\m *ama nar bistan t^ha -ma -ba =pi*
\g mother 2pl lunch eat -finish -nom =q1
\p *n. pron. n. v.t.&v.i. -s.v. -suff. =part.*

\f Mother, did you finish eating lunch? [CHUK221212D2A_0061]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0062

\ELANf 203.715

\ELANf 205.277

\ELANf Dorji Chojjom

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 203.715 205.277

\t *Bate^habaci. t^hotdaba. t^hama!*

\m *ba- t^ha -ba =ci t^hot -da -ba t^ha -ma*

\g *neg- eat -nom =cop.as make -keep -nom eat -imp*

\p *pref.- v.t.&v.i. -suff. =cop. v.t. -s.v. -suff. v.t.&v.i. -suff.*

\f (We) didn't eat yet. (I) made and kept it. Eat! [CHUK221212D2A_0062]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0063
\ELANf 205.277
\ELANf 206.874
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 205.277 206.874
\t *ʃa* *Tow* *ts^heriŋ*, *t^honma*.
\m *ja* *tow* *ts^heriŋ* *t^hon* *-ma*
\g go.ahead *Tow* *Tshering* take *-imp*
\p *interj.* *prop.n.* *prop.n.* *v.t.* *-suff.*

\f Go ahead, Tow Tshering, take it! [CHUK221212D2A_0063]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0064

\ELANf 205.277

\ELANf 206.874

\ELANf TowTshering

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 205.277 206.874

\t *Ama anut^he?* *t^ha-ba?* *inde?*, *ziŋkt^hondej?*

\m *ama onow* =*t^he?* *t^ha* *-ba?* *in* *-de?* *ziŋk* *-t^hon* *-de?=aj*

\g mother younger.brother=add eat -inf say -prs lead.along -take -prs=ok

\p *n.* *n.* =*clit.* *v.t.&v.i.* *-suff.* *v.t.&v.i.* *-suff.* *v.t.* *-s.v.* *-suff.-part.*

\f Mother, the younger brother too says (he) will eat, shall (I) take him along? [CHUK221212D2A_0064]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0065
\ELANf 206.874
\ELANf 207.531
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 206.874 207.531
\t *Hoj hoj naaj ho?*
\m *hoj hoj naη=aj ho?*
\g ok ok wait=ok ey
\p *interj. interj. interj. interj.*

\f Yes, yes, wait ok! [CHUK221212D2A_0065]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0066
\ELANf 207.531
\ELANf 208.308
\ELANf Sang Tshomo
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 207.531 208.308
\t *Ziŋkt^honma.* *tɕ^haziŋkma.*
\m *ziŋk* *-t^hon* *-ma* *tɕ^ha* *-ziŋk* *-ma*
\g lead.along -take -imp eat -lead.along -imp
\p *v.t.* *-s.v.* *-suff.* *v.t.&v.i.* *-s.v.* *-suff.*
\f Take him along. Take him along to eat. [CHUK221212D2A_0066]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0067
\ELANf 208.308
\ELANf 211.774
\ELANf Atha Kesang
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 208.308 211.774
\t *Hogaja.*
\m *hogaja*
\g it's.done(HIN)
\p *phrase*

\f It's done. [CHUK221212D2A_0067]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0068

\ELANf 208.308

\ELANf 211.774

\ELANf Dorji Chojjom

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 208.308 211.774

\t Ogi tepk^ho t^hawana! Naŋ ogi lecej awu, ŋomaraŋ.
\m ogi tep -k^ho t^ha- wa =na naŋ ogi le =ci=aj awu ŋoma =raŋ
\g that near -loc proh- move =conf 2sg that cop.le =cop.as=ok elder.sister really(<TB)=emph
\p dem. postp. -suff. pref.- v.i. =clit. pron. dem. cop =cop.=part. n. adv. =clit.

\f Just don't move close to that there! For sure you are that one, girl, really! [CHUK221212D2A_0068]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0069
\ELANf 211.774
\ELANf 212.621
\ELANf Sang Tshomo
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 211.774 212.621
\t *Ada?* *ga,* *mama tɕ^hawaju.*
\m *ada?* *ga* *mama tɕ^ha* *-wa -ju*
\g elder.brother come.imp food eat *-go -adh*
\p *n.* *imp.* *n.* *v.t.&v.i. -s.v. -suff.*

\f Boy, come, let's go and eat food. [CHUK221212D2A_0069]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0070

\ELANf 212.621

\ELANf 215.121

\ELANf Atha Kesang

\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 212.621 215.121

\t *Ama dzomo tat-da t^honmej.*

\m *ama dzomo tat -da t^hon -ma=aj*

\g mother Jomo approach -ipfv take -imp=ok

\p *n. prop.n. v.i. -suff. v.t. -suff.=part.*

\f Take (it) in the direction of Ama Jomo ok! [CHUK221212D2A_0070]

\ref CHUK221212D2A_0071
\ELANf 212.621
\ELANf 215.121
\ELANf TowTshering
\sound CHUK221212D2A.wav 212.621 215.121
\t *Hoj* *hoj.*
\m *hoj* *hoj*
\g *ok* *ok*
\p *interj.* *interj.*

\f Ok ok. [CHUK221212D2A_0071]

\ELANf CHUK221212D2A.wav
\ELANf audio/x-wav